

THE DISTRIBUTION OF THE GENERALIZED GREATEST
COMMON DIVISOR AND VISIBILITY OF LATTICE POINTS

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Abstract

For a fixed $b \in \mathbb{N} = \{1, 2, 3, \dots\}$, Goins et al. defined the concept of b -visibility for a lattice point (r, s) in $L = \mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{N}$ which states that (r, s) is b -visible from the origin if it lies on the graph of $f(x) = ax^b$, for some positive $a \in \mathbb{Q}$, and no other lattice point in L lies on this graph between $(0, 0)$ and (r, s) . Furthermore, to study the density of b -visible points in L , Goins et al. defined a generalization of greatest common divisor, denoted by \gcd_b , and proved that the proportion of b -visible lattice points in L is given by $1/\zeta(b+1)$, where $\zeta(s)$ is the Riemann zeta function. In this paper we study the mean values of arithmetic functions $\Lambda : L \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ defined using \gcd_b and recover the main result of Goins et al. as a consequence of the more general results of this paper. We also investigate a generalization of a result in the article of Goins et al. that asserts that there are arbitrarily large rectangular arrangements of b -visible points in the lattice L for a fixed b , more specifically, we give necessary and sufficient conditions for an arbitrary rectangular arrangement containing b -visible and b -invisible points to be realizable in the lattice L . Our result is inspired by the work of Herzog and Stewart who proved this in the case $b = 1$.

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1. Introduction

Let L denote the lattice $\mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{N}$. A point (r, s) in L is called *visible from the origin*, or simply *visible*, if $\gcd(r, s) = 1$, which is equivalent to having no other integer lattice points on the line segment joining the point $(0, 0)$ and the point (r, s) .

A classical result which predates the Prime Number Theorem asserts that the proportion of visible points in L is given by $1/\zeta(2) = 6/\pi^2 \approx 0.608$, where $\zeta(s)$ is the Riemann zeta function. In a recent paper [4], Goins et al. explore the visibility of lattice points on *generalized lines of sight*. Here, by generalized line of sight we mean that the line from the origin to the lattice point (r, s) is no longer a straight line segment but a more general curve. In particular, they study the density of b -visible points from the origin which are the points (r, s) in L that lie on the graph of $f(x) = ax^b$ where a is a rational number and b is a positive integer and no other point in L lies on this curve (i.e., line of sight) between $(0, 0)$ and (r, s) . Remarkably, they show (cf. [4, Theorem 1]) that the proportion of b -visible points in L is given by $1/\zeta(b + 1)$.

To study the density of b -visible points, they develop a generalization of the greatest common divisor.

Definition 1. Let $b \in \mathbb{N}$. The *generalized greatest common divisor* of r and s with respect to b is denoted by \gcd_b and is defined by

$$\gcd_b(r, s) := \max\{k \in \mathbb{N} \mid k \text{ divides } r \text{ and } k^b \text{ divides } s\}.$$

Notice that when $b = 1$, \gcd_b coincides with the classical greatest common divisor and one immediately recovers the classical result mentioned earlier pertaining to the proportion of visible points in L . Moreover, it is shown in [4] that a point $(r, s) \in L$ is b -visible if and only if $\gcd_b(r, s) = 1$.

In this work, we first begin by studying the mean values of arithmetic functions defined in terms of the \gcd_b . That is, for a fixed $b \in \mathbb{N}$ and an arithmetic function $f : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$, we define $\Lambda_f : L \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ to be

$$\Lambda_f(r, s) := f(\gcd_b(r, s)). \tag{1}$$

We let $M(\Lambda_f)$ denote the mean value of Λ_f over L (see Section 2 for the precise definition) and $\zeta_f(s) = \sum f(n) n^{-s}$ denote the Dirichlet series associated to f . Then our first result is as follows.

Theorem 2. Fix $b \in \mathbb{N}$ and let $f : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ be some arithmetic function satisfying

$$\frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N \frac{|(f * \mu)(k)|}{k} \rightarrow 0 \quad (N \rightarrow \infty), \tag{2}$$

where μ is the Mobius function and $*$ is the Dirichlet convolution. Then $M(\Lambda_f)$ exists and

$$M(\Lambda_f) = \frac{\zeta_f(b+1)}{\zeta(b+1)}, \tag{3}$$

as long as $\zeta_f(s)$ is absolutely convergent at $s = b + 1$. Moreover, the condition (2) holds, for example, when f is a bounded function.

Remark 3. We can recover the main result of [4] as an immediate application of Theorem 2 by letting $f(n) = \lfloor \frac{1}{n} \rfloor$.

As another consequence of Theorem 2 we have the following result which gives the density of the points $(r, s) \in L$ with a fixed \gcd_b .

Theorem 4. Fix two positive integers b and k . Then the proportion of points $(r, s) \in L$ for which $\gcd_b(r, s) = k$ is

$$\frac{1}{k^{b+1}\zeta(b+1)}.$$

We also study the average value of \gcd_b and obtain the following asymptotic formula.

Theorem 5. Fix $b \in \mathbb{N}$ with $b \geq 2$. Then

$$\sum_{\substack{0 < r \leq x \\ 0 < s \leq x^b}} \gcd_b(r, s) = x^{b+1} \frac{\zeta(b)}{\zeta(b+1)} + O(E(x)),$$

where

$$E(x) = \begin{cases} x^2 \log x & (b = 2) \\ x^b & (b > 2). \end{cases}$$

In the last part of this work, we explore a generalization of a result of Goins et al. [4, Theorem 2] that asserts that there are arbitrarily large rectangular arrangements in L consisting only of b -invisible points. More specifically, given an arbitrary rectangular arrangement consisting of b -visible and b -invisible points, which we call a b -pattern (see Definition 9), we provide necessary and sufficient conditions for it to be realizable in the lattice L . This generalization is motivated by the work of Herzog and Stewart, who in [5, Theorem 1] have completely characterized the conditions for a given pattern (in the case $b = 1$) consisting of visible and invisible points to be realizable in L . In particular, they showed that the lattice L contains arbitrarily large rectangular patches consisting entirely of invisible points. The following theorem which we prove in Section 3 generalizes Theorem 1 in [5] to our setting and completely characterizes the conditions for a given b -pattern to be realizable in L .

Before stating the theorem we need to introduce the following definition. Let m be a positive integer and S be any collection of m^{b+1} points in L . We say that S is a *complete rectangle modulo (m, m^b)* if it contains a complete system of residues of the Cartesian product $\mathbb{Z}/m\mathbb{Z} \times \mathbb{Z}/m^b\mathbb{Z}$.

Theorem 6. *For a fixed $b > 1$ let P be a b -pattern consisting of b -visible and b -invisible points. Then P is realizable in L if and only if the set of b -visible points in P fails to contain a complete rectangle modulo (p, p^b) for every prime p .*

In Section 3, we also give a number of immediate corollaries of this theorem which state whether or not certain b -patterns P can be realizable in L . Indeed, as a corollary we recover Theorem 2 in [4]:

Corollary 1. *L contains arbitrarily large rectangular patches consisting entirely of b -invisible points.*

Our paper is organized as follows. Section 2 contains the necessary definitions and the proofs of Theorem 2, Theorem 4 and Theorem 5. Section 3 provides a proof of Theorem 6 and discusses various consequences of this theorem.

2. Distribution of gcd_b

2.1. Mean Value of Arithmetic Functions of Generalized Greatest Common Divisor

For a positive integer N let

$$T_N := \{(r, s) \in L \mid 0 < r, s \leq N\}. \tag{4}$$

We define the mean value of a function $\Lambda : L \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ to be the limit

$$M(\Lambda) := \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sum_{(r,s) \in T_N} \Lambda(r, s)}{|T_N|}. \tag{5}$$

For an arithmetic function $f : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ we will be interested in functions $\Lambda_f : L \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ that are as in Definition 1. For these functions Theorem 2 shows that $M(\Lambda_f)$ can be computed in terms of the Dirichlet series $\zeta_f(s) = \sum f(n) n^{-s}$ associated to f and the Riemann zeta function $\zeta(s)$. When $b = 1$, the computation of $M(\Lambda_f)$ was previously considered in [7, Theorem 7]. We now present a proof of the theorem.

Proof of Theorem 2. Let u be the constant function $u(n) = 1$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Let g denote the Dirichlet convolution $f * \mu$ of f with the Möbius function μ so that $g * u = f$. Then $\Lambda_f = \Lambda_{g*u}$ and the number of times the term $g(k)$ (for a given

$k \in \mathbb{N}$) appears in the sum

$$q_N := \sum_{0 < r, s \leq N} \Lambda_{g * u}(r, s) = \sum_{0 < r, s \leq N} \left(\sum_{k \mid \gcd_b(r, s)} g(k) \right)$$

is $\lfloor \frac{N}{k} \rfloor \lfloor \frac{N}{k^b} \rfloor$. Therefore

$$q_N = \sum_{k=1}^N g(k) \left\lfloor \frac{N}{k} \right\rfloor \left\lfloor \frac{N}{k^b} \right\rfloor.$$

On the other hand,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{N^2}{k^{b+1}} - \left\lfloor \frac{N}{k} \right\rfloor \left\lfloor \frac{N}{k^b} \right\rfloor &= \frac{N}{k^b} \left(\frac{N}{k} - \left\lfloor \frac{N}{k} \right\rfloor \right) + \left\lfloor \frac{N}{k} \right\rfloor \left(\frac{N}{k^b} - \left\lfloor \frac{N}{k^b} \right\rfloor \right) \\ &\leq \frac{N}{k^b} + \left\lfloor \frac{N}{k} \right\rfloor \leq \frac{2N}{k}. \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

Then by our hypothesis on $g = f * \mu$ we have

$$\frac{|q_N - \sum_{k=1}^N g(k) \frac{N^2}{k^{b+1}}|}{N^2} \leq \frac{2N H_N}{N^2} \rightarrow 0,$$

where $H_N = \sum_{k=1}^N |g(k)|k^{-1}$. This implies

$$M(\Lambda_f) \rightarrow \zeta_g(b + 1).$$

The equality (3) follows now from the fact that $\zeta_f(s) = \zeta_g(s)\zeta(s)$ for every s for which $\zeta_f(s)$ and $\zeta(s)$ are absolutely convergent. \square

As another consequence of Theorem 2 we can also count the proportion of lattice points with a given \gcd_b . More specifically, fix two positive integers b and k . For $N > 0$ let T_N be the set defined in (4), then the proportion of lattice points with \gcd_b equal to k is defined by the limit

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{|\{(r, s) \in T_N \mid \gcd_b(r, s) = k\}|}{|T_N|}.$$

The value of this limit is given in Theorem 4, whose proof follows from Theorem 2 by taking $f : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ to be the function defined by $f(n) = k$ for $n = k$, and $f(n) = 0$ for $n \neq k$.

More generally, we obtain the following generalization to $b \geq 1$ of a result of Cohen [2, Corollary 3.2].

Corollary 2. *Let S be a subset of \mathbb{N} . Then the proportion of lattice points $(r, s) \in L$ for which $\gcd_b(r, s) \in S$ is given by $\zeta_S(1 + b)/\zeta(b + 1)$, where*

$$\zeta_S(b + 1) = \sum_{k=1, k \in S}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k^{b+1}}.$$

More precisely,

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{|\{(r, s) \in L \mid 0 < r, s \leq N, \gcd_b(r, s) \in S\}|}{N^2} = \frac{\zeta_S(b + 1)}{\zeta(b + 1)}.$$

2.2. The Average Value of General Arithmetic Functions in the Lattice

For a general function $\Lambda : L \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ we can still give a description of the mean value $M(\Lambda)$ in terms of a Dirichlet series whose k -th coefficient ($k > 0$) is the average value of Λ on the points with $\gcd_b = k$ for a fixed $b \in \mathbb{N}$. More specifically, we define

$$\zeta_{\Lambda, b}(s) := \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{M_{b, k}(\Lambda)}{k^s},$$

where the coefficient $M_{b, k}(\Lambda)$, $k > 0$, is the average value of Λ on the points having $\gcd_b = k$, i.e.,

$$M_{b, k}(\Lambda) := \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sum_{(r, s) \in T_{N, b, k}} \Lambda(r, s)}{|T_{N, b, k}|},$$

and

$$T_{N, b, k} := \{(r, s) \in L \mid 0 < r, s \leq N, \gcd_b(r, s) = k\}. \tag{7}$$

As an interesting note, we can give a formulation of $M_{b, k}(\Lambda)$ in geometric terms if we interpret the \gcd_b as a metric as follows. Given a point $A = (r, s)$ in $L' = L \cup \{(0, 0)\}$ we let $\|A\|_b := \gcd_b(r, s)$ if $A \neq (0, 0)$, and $\|A\|_b = 0$ if $A = (0, 0)$. We say that two nonzero points $A = (r_1, s_1)$ and $B = (r_2, s_2)$ in L are in the same b -curve of vision if

$$\left(\frac{r_1}{\|A\|_b}, \frac{s_1}{\|A\|_b^b} \right) = \left(\frac{r_2}{\|B\|_b}, \frac{s_2}{\|B\|_b^b} \right),$$

i.e., the points A and B both lie on the graph of $f(x) = ax^b$, for some positive rational number a .

For $A, B \in L'$ we define the metric

$$d_b(A, B) := \begin{cases} \left| \|B\|_b - \|A\|_b \right|, & \text{if } A \text{ and } B \text{ are in the same } b\text{-curve of vision,} \\ \|A\|_b + \|B\|_b, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

In particular, $d_b(O, A) = \|A\|_b$.

With this definition of metric, the ball centered at the origin having radius 1 is exactly the set of b -visible points from the origin. Moreover, the set of points whose

\gcd_b is a fixed integer k can be thought of as sphere of radius k centered at the origin:

$$S_k^b := \{ A \in L : \|A\|_b = k \}. \tag{8}$$

Furthermore, according to Theorem 4 the sphere S_k^b has density $1/(k^{b+1}\zeta(b+1))$.

With this notation, $M_{b,k}(\Lambda)$ can be thought of as the average value of Λ on the sphere S_k^b .

The following theorem informs us on how to calculate $M(\Lambda)$ from $\zeta_{\Lambda,b}$. We remark that [7] also has a description of $M(\Lambda)$ but in terms of certain multiple Dirichlet series.

Theorem 7. *Fix $b \in \mathbb{N}$ and let $\Lambda : L \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ be a bounded function. Then $\zeta_{\Lambda,b}(s)$ is convergent at $s = b + 1$ and*

$$M(\Lambda) = \frac{\zeta_{\Lambda,b}(b+1)}{\zeta(b+1)}. \tag{9}$$

Proof. We begin by showing that

$$M(\Lambda) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} M_k(\Lambda), \tag{10}$$

where $M_k(\Lambda)$ is defined as the limit

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sum_{(r,s) \in T_{N,b,k}} \Lambda(r,s)}{N^2}$$

and $T_{N,b,k}$ is as in (7).

In order to show this, we start with dividing the following identity by N^2

$$\sum_{0 < r,s \leq N} \Lambda(r,s) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \sum_{\substack{0 < r,s \leq N \\ \gcd_b(r,s)=k}} \Lambda(r,s),$$

thus obtaining

$$\frac{\sum_{0 < r,s \leq N} \Lambda(r,s)}{N^2} = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{S_{N,k}}{N^2}, \tag{11}$$

where

$$S_{N,k} = \sum_{\substack{0 < r,s \leq N \\ \gcd_b(r,s)=k}} \Lambda(r,s).$$

Let $C > 0$ such that $|\Lambda(r,s)| \leq C$ for all $(r,s) \in L$. Then

$$|S_{N,k}| \leq q_{N,b,k} C,$$

where $q_{N,b,k} = |T_{N,b,k}|$. Using the trivial bound

$$q_{N,k} \leq \left\lfloor \frac{N}{k} \right\rfloor \left\lfloor \frac{N}{k^b} \right\rfloor$$

we obtain the estimate

$$\frac{|S_{N,k}|}{N^2} \leq \frac{C}{k^{b+1}},$$

for all $N \geq 1$. The Weirstrass M -test allows us now to interchange the limit $N \rightarrow \infty$ in the infinite sum (11), thus obtaining (10).

Finally, (9) is a consequence of the identity

$$M_k(\Lambda) = \frac{M_{b,k}(\Lambda)}{k^{b+1} \zeta(b+1)},$$

which in turn follows by taking the limit as $N \rightarrow \infty$ in

$$\frac{S_{N,k}}{N^2} = \frac{S_{N,k}}{q_{N,b,k}} \frac{q_{N,b,k}}{N^2},$$

and observing that $q_{N,b,k}/N^2 \rightarrow 1/(k^{b+1}\zeta(b+1))$, by virtue of Theorem 4. \square

Clearly this theorem immediately implies Theorem 2 as $M_{b,k}(\Lambda_f) = f(k)$, for all $k > 0$, for Λ_f defined as in (1).

2.3. The Average Value of gcd_b

In this section we are going to study the average value of the gcd_b throughout the points of the lattice L in more detail. The case $b = 1$ has been previously considered in the paper [3] and asserts that

$$\sum_{r,s \leq x} \text{gcd}(r, s) = \frac{x^2}{\zeta(2)} \left(\log x + 2\gamma - \frac{1}{2} - \frac{\zeta'(2)}{\zeta(2)} \right) + O(x^{1+\theta+\epsilon}) \tag{12}$$

for every $\epsilon > 0$, where γ is the Euler constant and θ is the exponent appearing in Dirichlet's divisor problem, namely, θ is the smallest positive number such that for every $\epsilon > 0$

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \tau(n) = x \log x + (2\gamma - 1)x + O(x^{\theta+\epsilon}).$$

Moreover, it is known that $1/4 \leq \theta \leq 131/416$, where the upper bound was found by Huxley in [6] and it is the best upper bound for θ up to date.

The case $b \geq 2$ is treated in Theorem 5 whose proof we give below. We highlight that, unlike (12), Theorem 5 does not provide secondary error terms. We also point out that even though it is classical to consider the sum

$$\sum_{\substack{0 < r \leq x \\ 0 < s \leq x}} \text{gcd}_b(r, s),$$

it is more natural in this context to rather work with the sum

$$\sum_{\substack{0 < r \leq x \\ 0 < s \leq x^b}} \gcd_b(r, s).$$

Proof of Theorem 5. Let $b \geq 2$. From the classical identity $\sum_{d|n} \phi(d) = n$, $n \geq 1$ for the Euler totient function ϕ , we obtain the following identities

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\substack{0 < r \leq x \\ 0 < s \leq x^b}} \gcd_b(r, s) &= \sum_{\substack{0 < r \leq x \\ 0 < s \leq x^b}} \sum_{d | \gcd_b(r, s)} \phi(d) \\ &= \sum_{d \leq x} \phi(d) \left\lfloor \frac{x}{d} \right\rfloor \left\lfloor \frac{x^b}{d^b} \right\rfloor \\ &= \sum_{d \leq x} \phi(d) \left\{ \frac{x^{b+1}}{d^{b+1}} + O\left(\frac{x^b}{d^b}\right) \right\} \\ &= x^{b+1} \sum_{d \leq x} \frac{\phi(d)}{d^{b+1}} + O\left(x^b \sum_{d \leq x} \frac{\phi(d)}{d^b}\right). \end{aligned}$$

We now invoke the following estimates (cf. [1] Chapter 3, Exercises 6 and 7)

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \frac{\phi(n)}{n^2} = \frac{1}{\zeta(2)} \log x + \frac{\gamma}{\zeta(2)} - A + O\left(\frac{\log x}{x}\right), \tag{13}$$

where $A = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\mu(n) \log n}{n^2} = \frac{\zeta'(2)}{\zeta(2)^2}$, and

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \frac{\phi(n)}{n^\alpha} = \frac{\zeta(\alpha - 1)}{\zeta(\alpha)} + \frac{x^{2-\alpha}}{2-\alpha} \frac{1}{\zeta(2)} + O(x^{1-\alpha} \log x), \tag{14}$$

where $\alpha > 1$ and $\alpha \neq 2$.

Applying (13) and (14) to $b = 2$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\substack{r \leq x \\ s \leq x^2}} \gcd_2(r, s) &= x^3 \left\{ \frac{\zeta(2)}{\zeta(3)} - \frac{1}{x} \frac{1}{\zeta(2)} + O\left(\frac{\log x}{x^2}\right) \right\} + O(x^2 \log x) \\ &= x^3 \frac{\zeta(2)}{\zeta(3)} + O(x^2 \log x), \end{aligned}$$

and applied to $b \geq 3$ we similarly obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\substack{r \leq x \\ s \leq x^b}} \gcd_b(r, s) &= x^{b+1} \left\{ \frac{\zeta(b)}{\zeta(b+1)} + \frac{x^{1-b}}{1-b} \frac{1}{\zeta(2)} + O(x^{-b} \log x) \right\} + O(x^b) \\ &= x^{b+1} \frac{\zeta(b)}{\zeta(b+1)} + O(x^b), \end{aligned}$$

which proves the theorem. \square

3. The Graph of b -visible Points

The collection of all b -visible points in the lattice L can be thought of as a graph, denoted by G_b , if we build an edge between two given b -visible points whenever the Euclidean distance between them is 1. In this section we will prove some results concerning the connectivity of the graph G_b .

We start with the following result which states that G_b is on average $4/\zeta(b+1)$ -connected, i.e., every point in the graph G_b is on average connected to $4/\zeta(b+1)$ points.

Theorem 8. *For an arbitrary point in the lattice L , there are on average*

$$\frac{4}{\zeta(b+1)}$$

b -visible points around it. More precisely, for $(r, s) \in L$ define

$$\Lambda(r, s) = |\{(n, m) \in L \mid (n, m) \text{ is } b\text{-visible and } |n - r| + |m - s| = 1\}|,$$

and let $M(\Lambda)$ be as in (5). Then

$$M(\Lambda) = \frac{4}{\zeta(b+1)}.$$

Proof. Let $\Theta(r, s) = \left\lfloor \frac{1}{\gcd_b(r, s)} \right\rfloor$ for $(r, s) \in L$. Then

$$\Lambda(r, s) = \sum_{\substack{(n, m) \in L \\ |n-r|+|m-s|=1}} \Theta(n, m).$$

For an integer $N > 2$ we have that the sum

$$\sum_{0 < r, s \leq N} \Lambda(r, s)$$

equals

$$4 \sum_{0 < r, s \leq N} \Theta(r, s) - [\Theta(1, 1) + \Theta(1, N) + \Theta(N, 1) + \Theta(N, N)] - \sum_{i=1}^N [\Theta(1, i) + \Theta(i, 1) + \Theta(i, N) + \Theta(N, i)],$$

but since Θ is a bounded function we clearly have

$$\sum_{0 < r, s \leq N} \Lambda(r, s) = 4 \sum_{0 < r, s \leq N} \Theta(r, s) + O(N).$$

The result now follows from Theorem 2 applied to Θ and Remark 3. □

Despite the result above, we will show in Corollary 5 that the graph G_b is not connected, i.e., for every $b \geq 1$ there are b -visible points completely surrounded by b -invisible points. The connectivity of the graph G_1 was also studied by Vardi [8] in connection with the question of unbounded walks on a single subset of a graph which Vardi calls *deterministic percolation*. Vardi shows that there is a unique infinite connected component of G_1 , denoted by C_1 , which has an asymptotic density. In particular, Theorem 3.2 and 3.3 of [8] shows that the limit

$$\theta := \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{|C_1 \cap T_N|}{|T_N|}$$

exists and it is non-zero, where T_N is defined in (4). Moreover, his computations seem to indicate that the proportion of C_1 in G_1 is approximately $0.96 \pm .01$. Therefore $\theta \approx 0.58368$ which experimentally shows that more than 58% of lattice points lie in the infinite component.

Since $G_1 \subset G_b$ for $b \geq 2$, the results of [8] immediately imply that there is only one infinite connected component of G_b , which we denote by C_b . Moreover, this infinite connected component has positive density in G_b , i.e. there exists a constant $K > 0$ such that

$$K < \frac{|C_b \cap T_N|}{|T_N|}$$

for $N \gg 0$. In future work we would like show that the limit

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{|C_b \cap T_N|}{|T_N|}$$

exists for all $b > 1$ and compute it experimentally.

3.1. Patterns of b -visible and b -invisible Lattice Points

In [4, Theorem 2] it is shown that the lattice L contains arbitrarily large rectangles containing only b -invisible points. This raises the natural question: what other rectangular arrangements consisting of b -visible points and b -invisible points can be found in the lattice L ? In [5], Herzog and Stewart gave a complete answer to this question in the case $b = 1$. In this section we generalize their work to the case $b \geq 2$.

In order to make the geometrical representations easier to visualize, we will use the same notation as in [5] and assign a circle (o) for every b -visible point in the lattice and a cross (x) for every b -invisible point.

Definition 9. Let w be a positive integer and to each element $(r, s) \in L$ with $1 \leq r \leq w$ and $1 \leq s \leq w^b$ assign a cross or a circle or neither. We call this configuration a b -pattern P of L .

We say that the b -pattern P can be realized in L if there exists a point (u, v) in L such that the rectangle

$$(u, v) + P = \{ (r, s) \in L : u + 1 \leq r \leq u + w, v + 1 \leq s \leq v + w^b \}$$

has a b -visible point whenever P has a circle and a b -invisible point whenever P has a cross.

Definition 10. Let m be a positive integer. We call a *complete rectangle modulo* (m, m^b) any collection S of m^{b+1} points in L containing a complete system of residues of the Cartesian product $\mathbb{Z}/m\mathbb{Z} \times \mathbb{Z}/m^b\mathbb{Z}$.

In what follows, we will use the notation $(x, y) \equiv (r, s) \pmod{(m, m^b)}$ to mean that the congruences $x \equiv r \pmod{m}$ and $y \equiv s \pmod{m^b}$ both hold.

We are now ready to prove the main result in this section.

Theorem 11 (cf. Theorem 6). *A given b -pattern P is realizable in L if and only if the set C of circles in P fails to contain a complete rectangle modulo (p, p^b) for every prime p .*

Proof. Let (u, v) be an element in L . Assume that the b -pattern P is embedded in the square $1 \leq r \leq w, 1 \leq s \leq w^b$. Denote by $(u, v) + P$ the translate of every lattice point in the b -pattern P by (u, v) . If we assume that the b -pattern P is such that its set C of circles contains a complete rectangle modulo (p, p^b) for some prime p , then there exists an element (r, s) in $(u, v) + P$ for which $(r, s) \equiv (0, 0) \pmod{(p, p^b)}$. This implies that p divides $\gcd_b(r, s)$, and thus (r, s) is b -invisible. This contradicts that P is realizable in L , which proves the necessity of the condition.

Assume now that the set C of circles in P fails to contain a complete rectangle modulo (p, p^b) for every prime p . Then we will find a (u, v) in L such that $(u, v) + P$ contains a b -visible point for every circle of P and a b -invisible point for every cross in P . Such (u, v) will be found as a common solution to three collections of congruences that we define below.

We define the first collection of congruences as follows. Let p be a prime with $p \leq w$. The condition of the theorem implies the existence of a point (r_p, s_p) such that $(r, s) \not\equiv (r_p, s_p) \pmod{(p, p^b)}$ for all (r, s) in C . Let (u, v) be such that

$$(u, v) \equiv (-r_p, -s_p) \pmod{(p, p^b)}. \tag{15}$$

For all (r, s) in C we then have $(u+r, v+s) \equiv (r-r_p, s-s_p) \not\equiv (0, 0) \pmod{(p, p^b)}$, so that $\gcd_b(u+r, v+s)$ is not divisible by p . Since the moduli p in (15) are relatively prime, we can find a (u, v) so that (15) holds simultaneously for all $p \leq w$.

We build now the second collection of congruences. The idea for this collection is to guarantee that every cross in P becomes a b -invisible point in $(u, v) + P$. This is done as follows. To each cross (i, j) in the b -pattern P we associate a prime $Q(i, j) > w$, with different primes $Q(i, j)$ corresponding to different points (i, j) . To the congruences (15) we attach the congruences

$$(u, v) \equiv (-i, -j) \pmod{(Q(i, j), Q(i, j)^b)}, \tag{16}$$

for each cross (i, j) in the b -pattern P . The congruence (16) implies $(u + i, v + j) \equiv (0, 0) \pmod{(Q(i, j), Q(i, j)^b)}$. This implies that $Q(i, j)$ divides $\gcd_b(u + i, v + j)$, so that $(u + i, v + j)$ is b -invisible for every cross (i, j) in the b -pattern P . Once again, the Chinese Remainder Theorem guarantees the existence of a common solution (u, v) to (15) and (16).

Observe, additionally, that for this common solution (u, v) we have that the congruence $(u + r, v + s) \equiv (0, 0) \pmod{(Q(i, j), Q(i, j)^b)}$, for (r, s) with $1 \leq r \leq w$ and $1 \leq s \leq w^b$, has a solution if and only if (r, s) coincides with the cross (i, j) in P . This is a consequence of the inequalities $Q(i, j) > w$ and $Q(i, j)^b > w^b$.

The above considerations imply so far that for a circle (r, s) in P the number $\gcd_b(u + r, v + s)$ is not divisible by the primes $p \leq w$ and $Q(i, j)$. However, it may still happen that $\gcd_b(u + r, v + s) > 1$ for some circle (r, s) in P . We can remedy this by considering a third collection of congruences as follows.

First, fix a positive u satisfying both (15) and (16). The positive numbers $u + 1, \dots, u + w$ have a finite number of prime factors which, by the above considerations, are all different than the primes $p \leq w$ and $Q(i, j)$; we use q to denote these prime factors. For each one of these primes q we attach to (15) and (16) a new set of congruences

$$v \equiv 0 \pmod{q}, \tag{17}$$

which has a simultaneous solution by the Chinese Remainder Theorem. Moreover, since $q > w$ (and so $q^b > w^b$) we have that $v + 1, \dots, v + w^b$ lies between two multiples of q^b , namely v and $v + q^b$, therefore $v + s$ is not divisible by q^b for $1 \leq s \leq w^b$. In this way, for every circle (r, s) in C we have that $\gcd_b(u + r, v + s)$ is not divisible by any of the primes q . In conclusion, we have that $\gcd_b(u + r, v + s) = 1$, i.e., $(u + r, v + s)$ is b -visible for every circle (r, s) in C . This finishes the proof of the theorem. □

It is worth mentioning that since the criterion for a b -pattern P to be realizable in L is based on a collection of congruences, it immediately follows that if P is realizable once then it is realizable infinitely many times.

We finish by stating a collection of results that are consequences of Theorem 11.

Corollary 3 ([4, Theorem 2]). *Any b -pattern P containing only crosses is realizable in L , that is: L has arbitrarily large b -invisible forests.*

Corollary 4. *Let P be the b -pattern consisting of a square with vertices $(1, 1)$, $(N, 1)$, (N, N) and $(1, N)$, $N \geq 1$, containing only circles. Then P is realizable if and only if $N^2 < 2^b$.*

Corollary 5. *Any b -pattern P composed of crosses and only one circle is realizable in L , that is, there are extremely lonesome b -visible points. Therefore the graph G_b defined above is not connected.*

For example, the point $(6001645, 49747967748324)$ has $\gcd_2 = 1$, but the points around it which are $(6001645+i, 49747967748324+j)$ with $(i, j) = (-1, -1), (-1, 0), (-1, 1), (0, -1), (0, 1), (1, -1), (1, 0), (1, 1)$ have $\gcd_2 = 19, 6, 11, 13, 5, 17, 2, 7$ respectively.

Corollary 6. *Let P be the b -pattern that consists of a rectangle with vertices $(1, 1)$, $(M, 1)$, (M, N) and $(1, N)$, $M \geq 2$, $N \geq 2$, with all of its boundary points being circles and all its interior points being crosses. For $b = 1$, we have that P is realizable in L if and only if M and N are both odd (cf. [5, Corollary 3]). For $b \geq 2$, P is realizable in L if and only if M is odd or $N \geq 2^b$. In particular, there are arbitrarily large rectangular b -invisible forests fenced off by b -visible points.*

Proof. We will assume that $b \geq 2$, since the case $b = 1$ can be found in [5, Corollary 3].

Let $p > 2$ be a prime number. Take $z \pmod p$ such that $z \not\equiv 1, M, N \pmod p$. Then $(z, z) \pmod{(p, p^b)}$ cannot be congruent to any of the elements in the boundary of P which is described by the set

$$C := \{(1, s), (r, 1), (M, s), (r, N) : 1 \leq r \leq M, 1 \leq s \leq N\}.$$

Thus we have shown that C fails to contain a complete rectangle modulo (p, p^b) for $p > 2$. Therefore, for this specific pattern P we have that

$$P \text{ is realizable in } L \iff C \text{ fails to contain a complete rectangle mod}(2, 2^b). \tag{18}$$

With this new equivalency in mind we now proceed to prove the result. Suppose that P is realizable in L . Let us show that either M is odd or $N < 2^b$. Suppose not, i.e., M is even and $N \geq 2^b$. Then the following points of C

$$(1, 1), (1, 2), \dots, (1, 2^b) \quad \text{and} \quad (M, 1), (M, 2), \dots, (M, 2^b)$$

contain a complete rectangle mod $(2, 2^b)$. This is a contradiction according to (18).

Conversely, suppose that M is odd or $N < 2^b$. Let us show that P is realizable in L . According to (18) it is enough to show C fails to contain a complete rectangle mod $(2, 2^b)$. In order to do this, we will show that it is impossible for the set C to contain all of the elements

$$(2, 2), (2, 3), \dots, (2, 2^b) \pmod{(2, 2^b)}. \tag{19}$$

from a complete rectangle modulo $(2, 2^b)$. Indeed, if M is odd then only the points from C given by (r, N) , $1 \leq r \leq M$, could contain all of (19), but this is impossible as their second component is N which is fixed; recall that $2 < 2^b$ since we are assuming $b \geq 2$.

Finally, if $N < 2^b$ then none of the points in C is congruent to the pair $(2, 2^b) \pmod{(2, 2^b)}$ as they all have second component between 1 and $N (< 2^b)$. \square

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